

PHYTOCHEMICAL POTENTIAL AND DIAGNOSTIC FEATURES OF *ARTHROPHYTUM LONGIBRACTEATUM* KOROVIN

Nurmanbek A.E.

Al-Farabi Kazakh National University, Almaty, Republic of Kazakhstan

e-mail: aydyn.nurmanbek@gmail.com, tel.: +7 776 242 36 19

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Relevance: *Arthrophytum longibracteatum* Korovin is a rare species of the family Chenopodiaceae Less., growing in the arid ecosystems of Kazakhstan. This plant remains poorly studied in terms of pharmacognostic aspects, which highlights the necessity of its comprehensive investigation as a potential source of biologically active compounds.

Objective. To study the morphological, anatomical, and phytochemical features of *Arthrophytum longibracteatum* in order to determine its pharmacological potential.

Materials and Methods. Plant material (aerial parts) was collected during the flowering phase and dried in the foothills of the Buguty mountain range. Macroscopic and microscopic examinations of tissues were carried out, phytochemical screening (qualitative reactions, chromatography) was performed, and physicochemical parameters (moisture, ash content, extractive substances) were determined.

Results. The plant is a shrub 0.3–2.0 m tall with erect, knotty shoots. Leaves are cylindrically-awn-shaped, slightly curved, and sharply pointed. Conductive tissues in stems and roots are well developed.

Signs of xeromorphic adaptation were identified in leaves and stems: thick-walled epidermal cells, a developed cuticle, paracytic stomata, abundant water-storage parenchyma, and the presence of oxalate crystals in the mesophyll. Mechanical elements (collenchyma, sclerenchyma) and a well-developed vascular system were noted in the stem. Characteristic morphological and anatomical traits were established, allowing for reliable identification of raw material. Phytochemical analysis revealed the presence of saponins (0.7%), flavonoids (0.154%), tannins, and organic acids. Quality indices were determined: moisture – 5.7%; total ash – 27.5%; extractive substances – 42.4%.

Conclusions. The complex of morphological, anatomical, and phytochemical characteristics confirms the promise of *Arthrophytum longibracteatum* as a source of biologically active substances and provides a foundation for further pharmacological research.